

***Tabanus* (Diptera: Tabanidae) eggs, an alternative host of rice stem borer (SB) egg parasite *Telenomus dignus* (Hymenoptera: Scelionidae)**

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Telenomus spp. are common egg parasites of *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Wlk.) and *S. innotata* (Wlk.) SB in South and Southeast Asia. In 1978-84 we collected the eggs of horn flies (HF) *Tabanus* spp., which inhabit rice, maize, and coconut fields,

in 14 Philippine provinces. *Telenomus dignus* Gahan emerged from 85% of 94 HF egg masses. Eggs collected (6,751) and parasitization percentage (87) were highest in coconut fields followed by maize and rice fields (see table).

Tabanus spp. and SB oviposit on the tops of leaves. *T. dignus* attack both. Although HF eggs are longer and more slender than SB eggs, they are acceptable hosts to the parasitic wasps. HF eggs could maintain *T. dignus* in fields with low SB populations, and enhance its effectiveness as a natural enemy of SB. □

Chironomid, corixid, and ostracod pests of irrigated rice seedling roots

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We collected several aquatic arthropods in IRRI fields and kept them in glass aquaria to determine if they fed on rice. Two-week-old rice seedlings were suspended on foam sheets with their roots in the water. Three groups of aquatic invertebrates fed on rice roots — larvae (see figure) of seven species of chironomid midges dominated by *Chironomus kiensis* Tokunaga, nymphs and adults of a corixid water boatman *Micronecta quadristrigata* Breddin, and adult ostracod crustacean *Cypris* sp.

We evaluated damage at 0, 20, 40, 100, and 500 arthropods per seedling for 72 h. The corixid cut more root hairs, but damage did not increase beyond 20 adults/seedling. Chironomid and ostracod damage increased progressively with higher densities. Chironomid larvae damaged roots more than ostracods at equal densities. In the field, dapog-raised seedlings are particularly vulnerable to root damage because before transplanting, they grow for 2 wk on banana leaves without soil. □

Injury to rice seedling roots caused by chironomid midge larvae (arrow).

Incidence of parasitization by *T. dignus* on eggs of *Tabanus* spp. collected from 14 rice, maize, and coconut provinces in the Philippines, 1978-84.

Province, municipality	Sampling date	Parasitization ^a on <i>Tabanus</i> spp. eggs					
		Rice		Maize		Coconut	
		Eggs (no.)	Parasitization (%)	Eggs (no.)	Parasitization (%)	Eggs (no.)	Parasitization (%)
Cagayan							
Solana	23 Sep 1981	510	51	130	84	—	—
Mt. Province							
Banawe	27 Mar 1979	115	75	—	—	—	—
La Union							
Agoo	13 Oct 1982	106	67	—	—	520	65
San Fernando	14 Oct 1982	—	—	—	—	530	85
Pangasinan							
Bani	12 Oct 1982	120	78	—	—	260	81
Manaoag	31 Jan 1979	—	—	382	78	284	87
Laguna							
Los Baños	3 Mar 1979	84	38	120	85	—	—
	22 Feb 1982	—	—	356	33	—	—
	30 Jan 1984	142	91	650	43	—	—
	15 Feb 1984	108	87	108	78	—	—
Liliw	14 Sep 1979	—	—	—	—	910	78
Santa Rosa	16 Mar 1980	115	40	—	—	—	—
Batangas							
Malvar	7 Mar 1979	—	—	240	60	390	95
	7 Mar 1979	360	94	110	88	—	—
Tanauan	20 Aug 1980	98	50	340	64	650	17
Palawan							
Aborlan	24 Apr 1979	76	54	—	—	82	100
Iloilo							
Tigbauan	17 Jan 1978	310	78	285	44	1300	96
	21 Oct 1982	284	66	—	—	530	88
Oton	17 Jan 1978	81	42	—	—	—	—
	10 Nov 1978	—	—	—	—	324	100
Capiz							
Dumarao	17 Feb 1981	—	—	486	81	—	—
Agusan Del Sur							
Del Monte	26 Jul 1981	—	—	162	74	—	—
Bukidnon							
Pangantukan	10 Jul 1979	—	—	212	47	—	—
Zamboanga Del Sur							
Molave	4 Aug 1981	320	50	—	—	—	—
North Cotabato							
Kabacan	20 Mar 1980	—	—	—	—	484	100
South Cotabato							
Koronadal	24 Feb 1983	361	88	92	82	487	85
Total		3190	66	3673	72	6751	87

^aDash = no eggs collected and no parasitization.